

BOND DURABILITY BETWEEN GFRP BARS AND FRESH AND SEA WATER CONCRETE UNDER SEAWATER IMMERSION

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluated the bond durability between glass fiber reinforced polymer (GFRP) bars and concrete produced with freshwater (FW) and seawater (SW) using direct pullout tests after being exposed to seawater under different temperatures, namely 20 °C, 40 °C, and 60 °C. Unaged (reference) air-cured pullout specimens were also tested for the sake of comparison. After 1-year of aging, the bond strength results for FW composition were 5%, 16%, and 5% higher than the corresponding reference for environments 20 °C, 40 °C, and 60 °C, respectively, while for SW composition, were 82%, 39%, and 36% higher than corresponding reference at the same temperatures.

KEYWORDS

Bond behavior; bond durability; direct pullout test; seawater concrete; accelerated artificial aging

INTRODUCTION

Water is an indispensable natural resource with immeasurable environmental and socioeconomic value. Concrete production accounted for 9% of global industrial water withdrawals in 2012, and by 2050, 75% of the water demand for concrete production is expected to be in regions with water stress (Miller et al., 2018). Therefore, the need to explore new resources to save freshwater is evident. Saltwater represents almost 98% of all water on planet Earth and is a widely available and barely explored resource. In this context, studies on using seawater directly in the concrete composition have been growing and show great potential, e.g. (Kaushik & Islam, 1995; Mohammed et al., 2004; Tjaronge et al., 2014; Xiao et al., 2017; Younis et al., 2018).

Traditional steel reinforced concrete structures are susceptible to serious problems related to durability with the use of seawater. As seawater has a high concentration of chloride ions (Mohammed et al., 2004; Xiao et al., 2017; Younis et al., 2018), steel reinforcement can corrode, reducing the structure's service life. As an alternative, replacing steel reinforcement with fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) reinforcement may enable the direct use of seawater in reinforced concrete structures. Among the main advantages of FRP, high corrosion resistance, high longitudinal tensile strength, and its lightweight can be highlighted. Typically, glass fiber reinforced polymer (GFRP) bars are the most widely used due to their cost-effectiveness compared to the other solutions.

As previously shown by Nepomuceno et al. (2021), low levels of bond degradation between FRP bars and concrete can be observed under harsh environmental conditions such as saline solutions. Short- (Soares et al., 2020; Sun et al., 2020) and long-term (Khatibmasjedi, 2018) existing studies on the bond behavior of FRP bars to seawater concrete show a promising option and promote a more sustainable use of the available resources; however, there still needs more data regarding better understand this solution.

This study evaluates the bond durability of GFRP bars to concrete produced with freshwater (FW) and seawater (SW) through direct pullout tests (DPT) after being subjected to seawater immersion for 1-year at different temperatures, namely 20 °C, 40 °C and 60 °C. The results were compared with unconditioned (unaged) air-cured pullout specimens for both compositions (FW and SW). The

properties of concretes produced with FW and SW were also evaluated under the same conditions and exposure period.

This paper is divided into two main parts. Firstly, the experimental program is presented, introducing the materials used, the conditioning for accelerated aging of the specimens, and the adopted test methods. Secondly, the main results obtained are presented for each aging environment studied.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

The experimental program involved the use of (i) 24 concrete cubes to materialize the pullout specimens for the characterization of the bond between concrete and GFRP bars and (ii) 56 concrete cylinders for the assessment of concrete material properties, namely the elastic modulus, compressive and tensile splitting strengths. Table 1 shows the eight series tested. The denomination of each test series was defined as follows: (i) “FW” or “SW” represents the type of water used; (ii) “REF” or “1Y_X” represents the environmental condition, reference specimens, and 1-year exposure in seawater at X temperature, X being the temperatures of 20 °C, 40 °C, or 60 °C; and (iii) “i” represents the number of specimens tested under the same conditions. For example, “SW_1Y_60_3” is the third specimen of seawater concrete tested after one year of exposure to seawater at 60 °C.

Table 1: Experimental program

Concrete type	Age [day]	Environment	Number of specimens for type of characterization				Series denomination
			Elastic modulus [cylinder]	Compressive strength [cylinder]	Tensile splitting strength [cylinder]	Bond behavior [cube]	
FW	28	Air-cured	3	4	3	3	FW_REF_i
	365	Seawater at 20 °C	3	4	3	3	FW_1Y_20_i
		Seawater at 40 °C	3	4	3	3	FW_1Y_40_i
		Seawater at 60 °C	3	4	3	3	FW_1Y_60_i
SW	28	Air-cured	3	4	3	3	SW_REF_i
	365	Seawater at 20 °C	3	4	3	3	SW_1Y_20_i
		Seawater at 40 °C	3	4	3	3	SW_1Y_40_i
		Seawater at 60 °C	3	4	3	3	SW_1Y_60_i

Note: “i” represents the specimen number

Materials

The *ComBAR*[®] GFRP bars used as reinforcement in the pullout specimens have a ribbed round section and were produced by the *Schöck* company. GFRP bars are manufactured by the pultrusion process, with the glass fibers oriented in the pultrusion direction. The *ComBAR*[®] GFRP bars have a deformed external surface with ribs, a nominal diameter of 12 mm, and a cross-sectional area (A_b) of 113 mm². According to the technical information provided by the supplier, the ultimate tensile strength, f_{ult} , is equal to 1350 MPa, while the elastic modulus, E_i , is equal to 60 GPa.

Two concrete compositions were studied, being the only difference between them the type of water used in the mixture, namely freshwater (FW), obtained directly from the tap, and seawater (SW), obtained directly from the sea in Póvoa de Varzim (northern region of Portugal). According to the Portuguese Environment Agency (APA-ARH Norte), the quality of this seawater is classified as excellent, following the criteria established in Directive 2006/7/EC. The salinity of seawater in this region is around 3.5% (Zweng et al., 2019). The concrete mix compositions included the following components: (i) ordinary Portland cement (350 kg/m³), (ii) filler (80 kg/m³), (iii) sand (980 kg/m³), (iv) gravel 5-15 (812 kg/m³), (v) water (130 kg/m³), and (vi) Superplasticizer *Sika*[®] Viscocrete 650 DUO A (1.4 L/m³).

Accelerated aging

High temperatures were employed to simulate adverse environmental conditions for the accelerated aging process of the specimens. The specimens were exposed in three separate tanks filled with seawater, with each tank set to a different water temperature: 20 °C (room temperature), 40 °C, and 60 °C. The selection of 60 °C as the highest temperature was based on the glass transition (T_g) temperature of the GFRP bars. According to the American Concrete Institute (ACI 440.1R-15, 2015), typical FRP bars have a T_g ranging from 93 °C to 120 °C. The service temperature is recommended to remain at least 20 °C below the T_g to ensure optimal performance (Ascione et al., 2016). Therefore, the elevated temperatures in this study aimed to accelerate the aging process and induce potential degradation effects in the specimens under investigation.

Accelerated aging by immersion in seawater occurred 28 days after casting. During these initial 28 days, the specimens were air curing. The specimens were kept under these conditions for up to 1-year of exposure. Figure 1a shows the layout of the tanks used for the artificially accelerated aging of the specimens. Water circulation in the tanks was performed using an air pump, as shown in Figure 1c. Circulation of the water was performed every 3 hours during 3 minutes.

(a) Layout of the tanks at 40 °C and 60 °C

(b) Photo of the specimens in the tank 20 °C

(c) Water circulation scheme

Figure 1: Conditioning environments. Note: dimensions in millimeters

Test methods

The elastic modulus (E_c), compressive strength (f_c), and tensile splitting strength (f_{ct}) of concrete were evaluated according to the EN 12390-13 (2013), RILEM TC 148-SSC (1997), and EN 12390-6 (2009), respectively, using cylindrical concrete specimens with a diameter of 150 mm and a height of 300 mm. The initial evaluation (REF) of the mechanical properties of the two concrete compositions (SW and FW) was carried out at 28 days of concrete age. Afterward, the same properties were evaluated after 1-year of accelerated artificial aging in seawater under different temperatures. The setups for the tests used to characterize the concrete are presented in Figure 2.

The experimental setup for the direct pullout tests is illustrated in Figure 3. Pullout specimens were constructed with 12 mm nominal diameter (\emptyset) ribbed GFRP bars embedded in 200 mm edge concrete cubes with an anchorage length (L_b) of 5 times the diameter ($5\emptyset$). A load cell with a maximum capacity of 200 kN was used to measure the applied force during the tests. To assess the relative displacement (slip) between the GFRP and the concrete at the loaded end section, the average of displacements measured by LVDTs 1, 2, and 3 positioned at 120° around the GFRP bar was considered. Since the distance between the loaded end section and the section where the system holding the LVDTs was 200 mm, the elastic deformation of the GFRP bars between these two sections was accounted for the final slip. The free end slip was measured using LVDT 4. The stroke of LVDTs 1, 2, and 3 were ± 5 mm, while that of LVDT 4 was ± 10 mm. Tests were carried out under displacement control at a rate of 0.021 mm/s, as indicated by ASTM D7913/D7913M-14 (2020).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Concrete characterization

Table 2 presents the concrete characterization results in fresh and hardened states. Both compositions yielded similar results in the fresh state and met the S4 slump class, according to EN 206-1 (2007). In

the hardened state, the FW concrete presents higher mechanical performance than the SW concrete in terms of absolute values. According to EN 206-1 (2007), FW concrete meets with the strength class C25/30, while SW concrete meets with the strength class C20/25.

Table 2: Concrete properties (mean values)

Series	Slump [mm]	f_{cm} [MPa]	$f_{ctm,sp}$ [MPa]	E_{cm} [GPa]
FW_REF	165	33.7 (7%)	3.1 (6%)	25.4 (5%)
FW_1Y_20		39.9 (2%)	2.3 (10%)	26.6 (9%)
FW_1Y_40		45.3 (11%)	2.1 (8%)	28.1 (4%)
FW_1Y_60		44.8 (10%)	2.4 (7%)	29.1 (3%)
SW_REF	175	28.6 (1%)	2.0 (14%)	23.6 (4%)
SW_1Y_20		37.6 (2%)	2.3 (7%)	25.9 (4%)
SW_1Y_40		40.7 (6%)	2.2 (5%)	26.7 (3%)
SW_1Y_60		42.5 (1%)	2.0 (23%)	28.2 (2%)

Note: values in brackets are the coefficients of variation (CoV)

Figure 4 shows the evolution of the mechanical properties of concrete produced with freshwater (FW) and seawater (SW) after one year of immersion in seawater at 20 °C, 40 °C, and 60 °C. In general, the properties of the two concrete compositions showed an increase after 1-year of immersion in seawater; this may be a result of the continued hydration of the cement caused by the immersion of the specimens; other studies previously observed similar results, e.g., (Altalmas et al., 2015; Davalos et al., 2008).

Figure 4: Concrete mechanical properties

For all evaluated temperature conditions, the compressive strengths (Figure 4a) of specimens produced with FW are higher than those of specimens with SW. However, analyzing the increase in

compressive strength with the increase in temperature, it is observed that the specimens with SW present higher retention values. Compressive strength retention for FW concrete was 119%, 135%, and 133% for 20 °C, 40 °C, and 60 °C, respectively. On the other hand, SW concrete presents retentions of 132%, 143%, and 149% at the same temperatures, when compared with the corresponding results obtained at 28 days. Regarding the evolution of the elastic modulus, no significant variations were observed; however, for both compositions, a tendency of increasing the elastic modulus with increasing temperature was observed, as seen in Figure 4b.

However, a different behavior was observed in terms of the tensile splitting strength (Figure 4c): the concrete produced with FW showed a reduction of the properties with time, while SW concrete presented a slight increase. FW concrete's variation in tensile splitting strength was -25%, -32%, and -22% for 20 °C, 40 °C, and 60 °C, respectively, while in the case of SW, the variations were -2%, +8%, and +13%.

Bond behavior

Table 3 presents the average values obtained from the direct pullout tests, including: (i) maximum pullout force (F_{max}); (ii) loaded end slip at F_{max} (s_{lmax}); (iii) free end slip at F_{max} (s_{fmax}); (iv) bond strength (τ_{max}), assuming a constant shear stress along the anchorage length (ratio between F_{max} and contact area between the GFRP and concrete, see Eq. 1); (v) normalized bond strength (τ_n), calculated according to Eq. 2; (vi) residual pullout force (F_R) corresponding to a s_l of 10 mm; (vii) stiffness (K), obtained from the slope of the linear fitting performed on the pullout force *versus* loaded end slip curves in the range 10% to 30% of the maximum pullout force; (viii) fracture energy (G_f) during pullout process up to 10 mm of s_l ; (ix) F_R/F_{max} ratio; and (x) failure modes (FM).

Table 3: Direct pullout test results (mean values)

Series	F_{max} [kN]	s_{lmax} [mm]	s_{fmax} [mm]	τ_{max} [MPa]	τ_n [MPa]	F_R [kN]	K [kN.mm]	G_f [kN.mm]	F_R/F_{max} [%]	FM
FW_REF	34.4 (15%)	0.71 (33%)	0.35 (43%)	15.2 (15%)	2.6 (15%)	10.5 (23%)	96.8 (11%)	170.4 (18%)	30.3 (8%)	PO ³
FW_1Y_20	36.0 (13%)	0.84 (19%)	0.61 (16%)	15.9 (13%)	2.5 (13%)	8.8 (25%)	112.8 (23%)	167.5 (24%)	24.1 (12%)	PO ³
FW_1Y_40	40.1 (10%)	0.81 (13%)	0.48 (15%)	17.7 (10%)	2.6 (10%)	18.3 (35%)	155.2 (23%)	239.7 (24%)	45.3 (30%)	PO ² ; PR ¹
FW_1Y_60	36.2 (11%)	0.76 (8%)	0.51 (24%)	16.0 (11%)	2.4 (11%)	20.6 (53%)	156.3 (23%)	244.3 (34%)	55.2 (41%)	PR ³
SW_REF	19.7 (18%)	1.01 (10%)	0.81 (13%)	8.7 (18%)	1.6 (18%)	4.3 (11%)	49.1 (61%)	89.7 (21%)	21.8 (8%)	PO ³
SW_1Y_20	35.8 (2%)	0.77 (5%)	0.56 (6%)	15.8 (2%)	2.5 (2%)	8.7 (5%)	147.2 (41%)	167.3 (4%)	24.2 (7%)	PO ³
SW_1Y_40	27.5 (6%)	0.60 (9%)	0.50 (12%)	12.1 (6%)	1.8 (6%)	5.4 (17%)	273.5 (13%)	112.8 (10%)	19.6 (15%)	PO ³
SW_1Y_60	26.7 (20%)	0.77 (10%)	0.62 (13%)	11.8 (20%)	1.8 (20%)	6.6 (47%)	159.2 (7%)	118.1 (32%)	23.9 (27%)	PO ³

Note: values in brackets are the coefficients of variation (CoV). Failure modes: PO – pullout failure at the interface concrete/GFRP; PR – pullout failure at the interface concrete/GFRP with partial rupture of GFRP ribs; the values in superscript are the number of specimens where this failure mode occurred

$$\tau_{max} = \frac{F_{max}}{\pi \cdot \phi \cdot L_b} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

$$\tau_n = \frac{\tau_{max}}{\sqrt{f_{cm}}} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

The mean curves of the pullout force *versus* loaded end slip relationships for each conditioning studied, namely the reference and immersion in seawater at 20 °C, 40 °C, and 60 °C, are shown in Figure 5. Similar behavior is observed for both compositions (FW and SW) at all temperatures studied, characterized by pre-peak and post-peak phases. Initially, the bond is governed by chemical adhesion and lasts when the maximum force is achieved. In the downward phase, the friction between the materials is the main bond resisting mechanism, in almost all cases, except for curves FW_1Y_40

and FW_1Y_60, in which, in addition to friction, it was possible to observe the performance of the mechanical interlocking mechanism, where the ribs play an important role.

Figure 5: Pullout force *versus* loaded end slip

Two different failure modes were observed in the direct pullout tests: (i) pullout failure at the interface concrete/GFRP (see Figure 6a) and (ii) pullout failure at the interface concrete/GFRP with partial rupture of GFRP ribs (see Figure 6b). The first failure mode was the most commonly observed. However, in one specimen of FW_1Y_40 and all FW_1Y_60, the pullout failure was followed by partial rupture of the ribs. Similar behavior was observed in other studies, e.g. (Achillides & Pilakoutas, 2004; Soares et al., 2020), and it was indicated that the “wedging effect” may have occurred, probably due to the improvement in the mechanical properties of the concrete. In pullout (PO) failures, it is possible to observe the concrete tied to the ribs of the GFRP bar, which are intact, as shown in Figure 6a. In the second case, Figure 6b, the opposite is observed, layers of the GFRP bar are tied to the concrete, and the ribs are partially broken.

Figure 6: Failure modes

Figure 7 presents the average values and the retentions concerning the reference values of the direct pullout tests. In general terms, FW concrete yielded better bond performance than SW concrete. Specimens with FW instead of SW shown higher values of F_{max} (Figure 7a) and τ_{max} (Figure 7b), i.e. 74%, 1%, 46%, and 35% higher, for the series REF, 1Y_20, 1Y_40, and 1Y_60, respectively. Considering the bond strength retention, the SW composition performed better than the FW composition. The bond strength (τ_{max}) retention of the FW compositions was 5%, 16%, and 5% for immersion in seawater at 20 °C, 40 °C and 60 °C, respectively. In the case of SW specimens, retentions of 82%, 39%, and 36% were obtained at 20 °C, 40 °C, and 60 °C, respectively.

Regarding the ratio of residual force to maximum force (F_R/F_{max}), a considerable variation is observed for the FW specimens at temperatures of 40 °C and 60 °C, as shown in Figure 7c. In these cases, there were changes in the failure mode, and higher residual forces were achieved due to the better performance of the mechanical bond mechanism (related to the ribs failure mobilization) in the post-peak phase.

To disregard the influence of concrete compressive strength in results, Figure 7d presents normalized bond strength values. In this case, different behavior is observed between the compositions with FW and SW. The normalized bond strength results for FW specimens remain constant with increasing temperature, with a maximum variation of -10% concerning the reference. Similar behavior was observed in the case of SW, except in the series SW_1Y_20.

Regarding fracture energy (see Figure 7e), both compositions showed increases in the retentions. In the SW specimens, there was a maximum increase of 87% when exposed to seawater at 20 °C, while the FW specimens show a tendency to increase with increasing temperature. The bond stiffness (see Figure 7f) in both cases (FW and SW) showed retention values higher than 100%, being more relevant in the case of SW specimens. In this case, the chemical adhesion between the materials may have improved with increasing temperature, and the stress required to mobilize the GFRP bar to slide was larger.

Figure 7: Experimental results obtained from direct pullout tests

Based on the results obtained from the direct pullout tests, it is possible to verify that when FW is used instead of SW in the concrete composition, higher absolute values are obtained in all the evaluated parameters except for the stiffness. However, after 1-year of exposure to seawater at room temperature (20 °C), the specimens produced with SW yielded F_{max} , τ_{max} , F_R/F_{max} , τ_n , and G_f results similar to those produced with FW. Furthermore, the bond stiffness of the specimens produced with SW and immersed in seawater for 1-year showed higher values than those produced with FW.

When the obtained test results are analyzed in terms of retention properties, the specimens produced with SW shown superior bond mechanical performance to those obtained by the specimens produced with FW in several of the analyzed parameters, indicating a good performance, even in adverse conditions.

Concrete strength vs. bond behavior

Concrete compressive strength is a crucial parameter among various factors influencing the bond strength. An increase in concrete compressive strength is anticipated to result in a corresponding enhancement of bond strength. Consequently, several formulations have been proposed to predict bond strength based on a proportional relationship with concrete compressive strength, as established by standards such as ACI 440.1R-15 (2015), CSA S806-12 (2012), EN 1992-1-1 (2021). Figure 8 illustrates the relationship between concrete compressive strength and bond strength. As anticipated, an increase in concrete compressive strength led to a proportional enhancement in bond strength. The fitting lines in the figure clearly demonstrate this correlation.

Figure 8: Bond strength vs. concrete strength (f_{cm})

Additionally, increasing the concrete compressive strength affected the bond failure mode during the pullout tests, as shown in Figure 6. In the concretes with higher strengths (FW_1Y_40 and FW_1Y_60), visible damage occurred in the GFRP bars. Conversely, in cases involving concrete with lower strengths, the GFRP bars remained undamaged. These observations emphasize the influence of concrete compressive strength on the failure behavior of the bond interface.

In this study, all specimens exhibited failure at the concrete-matrix interface. However, based on previous findings by Lee et al. (2008), it is expected that a continued increase in concrete strength will result in a shift in failure location towards the fiber-matrix interface, both interfaces are identified in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Interfacial bond failure (adapted from (Lee et al., 2008))

CONCLUSIONS

This study evaluated the bond durability between GFRP bars and concrete produced with freshwater (FW) and seawater (SW) under the effect of conditioning to seawater at different temperatures. Specimens were air-cured for up to 28 days of age and then immersed in seawater at 20 °C, 40 °C, and 60 °C for 1-year before being tested. Additionally, the main mechanical properties of concrete produced with FW and SW were also tested under the same conditions.

From the tests carried out in the concrete characterization, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- i. The tests carried out at 28 days of age showed that the FW concrete presented higher values of compressive strength (+18%), elastic modulus (+7%), and tensile splitting strength (+52%) than SW concrete;
- ii. Regardless of the type of concrete, the compressive strength and elastic modulus tend to increase with increased temperature;
- iii. FW concrete showed reductions of up to 32% for the tensile splitting strength, while SW concrete showed a tendency to increase for higher temperature.

The main conclusions obtained from the direct pullout tests are as follows:

- i. Considering absolute values, FW specimens showed better performance than SW specimens. However, considering the analysis based on retention properties, SW specimens showed higher retentions than FW specimens in almost all the analyzed parameters;
- ii. Two types of failure modes were observed, namely pullout failure and pullout failure with partial rupture of the GFRP ribs. Accelerated aging did not change the failure mode of SW specimens. However, the FW specimens subjected to 40 °C and 60 °C had their failure modes changed from pullout to pullout failure with partial rupture of the GFRP ribs;
- iii. After 1-year submerged in seawater at room temperature, the FW and SW specimens achieved similar results in terms of F_{\max} , τ_{\max} , F_R/F_{\max} , τ_n , and G_f .

The results obtained seem to indicate that the use of seawater for the production of GFRP-reinforced concrete structures in the marine environment seems feasible and contributes to reduce the use of a scarce resource like the freshwater.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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